

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.20772708

Relationship Among Parental Involvement, Socioeconomic Background And Academic Achievement Of Public Senior Secondary School Students In North-Central Nigeria

¹ GIDADO, Bello Kumo, ² APEH, Hosea Abalaka & ³ ERI, Bernice Olohitai

Department of Educational Foundations,
University of Abuja, Abuja, Nigeria

Emails: gbkumo@gmail.com, apehhoseah@gmail.com & berniceeri80@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship among parental involvement, socioeconomic background and academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in North-Central Nigeria. Six objectives, three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. A correlational survey research design was employed in the study. The population of the study comprised 748,067 senior secondary school students (male and female) drawn from public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria. A sample size of 384 senior secondary students was selected for the study. The proportionate sampling technique was employed for the study. Two self-structured questionnaires, which were validated by experts at the University of Abuja, and academic scores from the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WAESSCE) 2020 – 2024 sessions were used for data collection. After a pilot test was conducted, Cronbach's Alpha statistics were used to determine the reliability of the questionnaires, which yielded reliability indexes of 0.628 and 0.642. The data collected was analysed using mean score and standard deviation for research questions, while hypotheses were tested using PPMCC and multiple regression analysis. The findings revealed high parental involvement among secondary school students in North-central Nigeria. Findings also showed a low socioeconomic background among senior secondary school students in North-Central, Nigeria. The findings equally revealed that the academic achievements of students in North-Central, Nigeria, in WAEC results from 2020 - 2024 academic sessions, though high, had some level of fluctuation within the four years. It was recommended that parents and guardians should sustain their level of involvement in their children's education by periodically communicating with the school on appropriate strategies for addressing any challenges that their children may face in school. School administrators and other stakeholders should provide aids and support such as scholarships, grants, financial assistance, free tutoring, or mentorship programmes to students from low socioeconomic backgrounds. Administrators and teachers should establish a system that monitors the progress of students' performance while also considering the impact of home and school-related factors that are equally part of the root causes in the fluctuation in academic achievement of students.

Keywords: Parental Involvement, Socioeconomic Background, Academic Achievement,

INTRODUCTION

Education is viewed primarily as a tool of transformation within a society. According to Brodowicz (2024), education is a way of improving the general well-being of people and society. It is an instrument that can improve the general well-being and productivity of learners and impact society positively. Apeh et al. (2023) highlighted that learners acquire a wide range of essential skills and socio-cultural virtues from the school, which prepares and propels them for the world of work and equally makes them responsive to their immediate environment and the larger society. Emaimo et al. (2019) emphasise that education is a means to higher economic achievement for individuals, families, society and the country as a whole. Education is a critical factor in determining an individual's prospects, including their career opportunities and earning potential (Kim et al., 2023). Thus, the educational outcome of adolescents remains a major concern to educators, policymakers, and parents alike, as it serves as an essential criterion for their future accomplishments.

Over the years, researchers have reported numerous factors, such as school size, assessment methods, social roles, grading systems, qualification of the teacher, teaching methods, students' externalising and internalising behaviour, educational materials, school facilities, family environment, among others, that influence students' academic outcomes (Brew et al., 2021). However, within the last decade, family environment variables such as parental involvement and socioeconomic background have attracted consistent attention in educational research due to their profound and interrelated effects on a child's academic success (Razzaq et al., 2024; Utami, 2022; Eriksson et al., 2021; Oba-Adenuga, 2020). Studies such as Gidado and Diffang (2024) have highlighted that the interaction of various socioeconomic, cultural, political, structural and psychological dispositions of a student's family background can go a long way in swaying and determining their personal conduct, which could apparently manifest in their behaviour and could equally be transmitted to the school environment. Gidado and Anyio (2025) emphasised that the family, irrespective of its sociocultural environment, is an essential part of every child's life since parental influences from the home could make or mar children's behavioural pattern.

Parental involvement is an unclear term that can have several meanings to different people (Kantova, 2024). Parental involvement is most effective when viewed as a partnership between educators and parents. It is a family concept that involves parents dedicated commitment and proactive engagement with their children's educational journey, both at home and in collaboration with the school (Oranga et al., 2023). In Nigeria, levels of parental involvement vary widely due to factors such as literacy levels, employment demands, and cultural expectations. Some parents actively engage in their children's education by providing emotional support, guidance, providing necessary school supplies, assisting with homework, modelling desired behaviour, engaging in reading activities with their children and maintaining an open dialogue about school events and experiences (Umeana, 2017), while others may be less involved due to time constraints or lack of awareness. Umeana further identified eight variables that characterize parent's active involvement in their children's education: providing emotional support, guidance, and resources, providing necessary school supplies, assisting with homework, modeling desired behavior, engaging in reading activities with their children and maintaining an open dialogue about school events and experiences Parental engagement should go beyond the home setting to attending school parent-teacher conferences or other school functions, serve on school boards (Belay & Galata, 2016), fund school project and volunteer in classroom activities.

Children whose parents consistently participate in their education tend to achieve higher academic grades compared to those whose parents are less involved (Reich et al., 2013). Similarly, when parents are actively involved in their child's education there is a greater likelihood that schools to a great extent benefit tremendously. There is teacher morale enhanced, positive evaluation of teachers by parents and improved reputation within the community (Umeana, 2017).

Parental high educational expectations for children have the strongest impact on academic performance compared with other types of parental involvement constructs, such as participation in school events, parent-child communication and help in homework (Sandeep & Choudhuri, 2017). Similarly, Kantova (2024) highlighted that higher parental involvement is associated with an increased probability of high

school graduation, while stricter parental behaviour is found to decrease the expected likelihood of completing high school. Notwithstanding, there is still a limited body of knowledge regarding which aspects of parental involvement improve students' education and what components of this involvement are more crucial.

Parents' socioeconomic background is a vital determinant of the academic success of students (Pal et al., 2016). Parents need available resources to provide their children with a variety of services and goods that can positively improve their all-around development. Socio-economic status is the social and financial status of individuals or family members within a particular society (Munir et al., 2023). Socio-economic status can be measured using indicators such as income level of parents, parental education, and occupational status, which reflect an individual's access to resources and social prestige (Pal et al., 2016). Machebe et al. (2017) reported that the educational development of students in Japan was relatively the same irrespective of their parents' high, medium or low level of income. Their report further revealed that there is no positive relation between family income and students' academic achievement, and that the low socioeconomic background of parents did not limit the number of children who got enrolled in school. However, Aina (2023) reported that disparity in income, education levels and occupational status among families in Nigeria creates unequal access to educational resources. These economic inequalities are aggravated by regional disparities and the growing population of out-of-school children (Ololade et al., 2023). Students from higher socioeconomic backgrounds are more likely to attend better-equipped schools, have access to good nutrition, better educational resources, private tutoring and enjoy more stable living conditions conducive to learning. In contrast, students from low socioeconomic families may face numerous challenges, including attending under-resourced schools, financial constraints that lead to the inability to purchase school materials, lack of study materials, poor nutrition, poor learning conditions, limited access to academic support and the pressure to contribute to household income through child labour, all of which could hinder performance (Pal, 2016).

According to Nato (2016), the family is still the bedrock of a child's ability to succeed in his academic work. Gidado and Diffang (2023) opined that the family is an essential, responsive and fundamental unit of society with the cardinal responsibility of improving every member of the unit positively for the betterment of society, including those within the immediate environment of the family. While numerous studies have highlighted the implications of parental involvement in improving academic outcomes (Meadan et al., 2014; Utami, 2022; Oranga et al., 2023), most existing studies have focused on Western or urbanised settings, often neglecting context-specific variables relevant to African societies, particularly in North Central Nigeria. In the Nigerian context, by focusing on public senior secondary school students in North Central Nigeria, this study aims to fill this gap and provide contextually relevant insights that can inform educational policy, family interventions, and community support programs in the study area.

Previous studies have widely explored several school-related factors (school infrastructure, teacher quality and more) and individual factors that influence the academic achievement of senior secondary students in North Central Nigeria. A broad review of literature indicates that less attention has been given to the relationship among parental involvement, socio-economic background and academic achievement of senior secondary school students. Besides these, studies are often fragmented, focusing on these variables in isolation and rarely considering how these family factors intersect in shaping student performance. Furthermore, few studies have adequately contextualised their findings within the cultural, economic, and social realities of North Central Nigeria.

Statement Of The Problem

The issue of fluctuating performance of senior secondary school students in standardised examinations such as the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) and the National Examination Council (NECO) has been a growing concern among educational stakeholders. For example, the first series of WAEC results released, which was conducted in 262 centres across Nigeria from January/February 2023, showed that only 23.99% of those who sat for the exam had credit and above, including English language and mathematics. The percentage of those who sat for the same exam in 2021 and 2022 had 30.11% and 26.32%, respectively, which includes the FCT (Guardian Newspaper in Gidado

& Diffang, 2024). Despite the several ongoing educational reforms and interventions by the Nigerian government in improving access and quality of education at all levels (from primary to tertiary), students' academic outcomes still seem to be unstable, particularly in the North-central geopolitical zone of Nigeria. This occurrence seems to raise concern about the relationship among parental involvement, socio-economic background and academic achievement of senior secondary school students.

Factors revolving around parental involvement, socio-economic background may have a striking effect on students' school performance over some school-related factors, bearing in mind that the school have these students 8 to 9 hours a day, far below 24 hours of the day. And some of the school duration could comprise assemblies, break periods, games, not to mention the peculiarity of frequent public holidays that are often observed in Nigeria. The link between the home and the school is the parent, and through their involvement in educating the child, they can assist the school in realising its objectives for the child. The extent to which parents get involved in their children's education through activities like helping with homework, attending school meetings, or setting academic expectations varies significantly, which is often shaped by their socio-economic status and educational attainment. Socioeconomic challenges such as poverty, low parental education levels and limited access to educational resources can restrict students' learning opportunities and contribute to poor academic performance.

Considering the shifting family composition, varying levels of parental involvement and economic inequality, the need for a comprehensive understanding of how these family variables may jointly associate with students' academic achievement in North-central Nigeria has become a key factor that requires urgent investigation. In view of the above, this study seeks to explore the relationship among parental involvement, socio-economic background and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North Central Nigeria. The understanding of these interrelated factors may help educators, government, parents, policymakers and researchers employ interventions that support students' academic performance and close existing educational gaps in North Central Nigeria.

Objectives

- I. Find out the extent of parental involvement of senior secondary school students in North -central Nigeria
- II. Find out the socioeconomic background of senior secondary school students in North-central Nigeria.
- III. Examine the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central Nigeria.
- IV. Examine the relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central Nigeria.
- V. Examine the relationship between socioeconomic background and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North Central Nigeria.
- VI. Determine the relationship among parental involvement, socioeconomic background and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central Nigeria.

Research Questions

- I. What is the extent of parental involvement in the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North Central Nigeria?
- II. What is the socioeconomic background of senior secondary school students in North-central Nigeria?
- III. What is the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central Nigeria?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between socioeconomic background and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship among parental involvement, socioeconomic background and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North Central Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Design

The research design adopted for this study is the Correlational design. The Correlational design allows the researcher to find out the extent of the relationship that exists between two or more variables. Correlational design is the most adequate when investigating relationships between dependent and independent variables without the researcher controlling or manipulating any of the variables (Bhandari, 2023).

Population

The population for this study is 748,067 (males and females) students drawn from the public senior secondary schools in North Central States of Nigeria, namely, Benue, Kogi, Kwara, Niger, Nassarawa, Plateau and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) Abuja.

Sample Size and Sampling Procedure

The sample size for this study consists of 384 senior secondary students (male and female) in North-Central Nigeria. The sample size was determined using Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) table for determining sample size for a specific population. The Krejcie and Morgan Table help the researcher to determine the sample size of a population (Qhaireenizzati 2017).

Instrumentation

Three research instruments were used for the study. Two self-structured questionnaires and students' academic scores from 2020 to 2024 West Africa Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) were used for the study.

The first instrument was a 14-item self-structured questionnaire titled: Extent of Parental Involvement of Senior Secondary School Students Questionnaire (EPISSSQ). The questionnaire enabled the researcher to find out the extent of parental involvement among senior secondary school students in North-central Nigeria. The questionnaire was prepared on a four-point scale of VHE –Very High Extent (4-points), HE - High Extent (3-points), LE - Low Extent (2-points), VLE – Very Low Extent (1 point).

The second instrument was a 10-item self-structured questionnaire titled: Socio-economic Background of Senior Secondary School Students Questionnaire (SEBSSSQ). The questionnaire enabled the researcher to find out the socio-economic background of senior secondary school students in North-central Nigeria. The questionnaire was prepared on a four-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (4-points), Agree (3-points), Disagree (2-points) and Strongly Disagree (1 point).

The third instrument was the academic record of students from WAEC and was used to measure students' academic achievement in Mathematics and English Language, drawn from the 2020 to 2024 West Africa Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) in North Central, Nigeria.

The two self-structured questionnaires were subjected to face and content validity by experts in the Department of Educational Foundations, University of Abuja. To determine the reliability of the questionnaires, a pilot study of the test-retest method of pilot testing was carried out within 14days. The reliability coefficient of the pilot test for the questionnaires was determined using the Intra-class Correlation Coefficient (ICC) and Cronbach's Alpha, which yielded a moderate value of 0.628 for EPISSSQ and 0.642 for SEBSSSQ.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected for this study were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Mean score and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficients (r) and multiple regression analysis were used to test the hypotheses.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *What is the extent of parental involvement in the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North Central Nigeria?*

Table 1: Extent of Parental Involvement in the Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in North Central Nigeria

N=384				
S/N	Statements	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
1	My parent(s) assist with my homework	2.94	.420	High extent
2	My parents spend quality time counselling me on my academic goals	2.76	.508	High extent
3	My parents restrict my screen time (time spent on television, phone/computer games) during weekdays	2.85	.540	High extent
4	My parents monitor my school grades regularly	2.74	.449	High extent
5	My notebooks are checked regularly by my parents	2.67	.572	High extent
6	My parents provide all the resources for my school	2.57	.569	High extent
7	My parents insist I learn a skill	2.73	.487	High extent
8	My parents attend PTA meetings regularly	2.66	.511	High extent
9	My parents visit my class often to check my academic progress	2.66	.542	High extent
10	My parents regularly come to verify my academic progress with my class teachers	2.54	.553	High extent
11	My parents always support my school projects financially	2.76	.516	High extent
12	My parents do not hesitate to pay my school fees	2.58	.555	High extent
13	My parents ensure I attend school regularly	2.49	.545	Low extent
14	My parents ensure I go to school early	2.46	.534	Low extent
Sectional Mean		2.67	0.73	High extent

As shown in Table 1, the extent of parental involvement of senior secondary school students in North Central Nigeria was presented. The Table shows a sectional mean of 2.67, which indicates that over an average of the respondents agreed to a great extent of parental involvement, except for items 13 and 14, which had a low extent. Therefore, there is high parental involvement among senior secondary school students in North-central Nigeria.

Research Question Two: *What is the socioeconomic background of senior secondary school students in North Central Nigeria?*

Table 2. Socioeconomic Background of Senior Secondary School Students in North Central Nigeria N=384

S/N	Statements	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
1	My parents have sufficient financial resources to meet my family's basic needs (food, shelter, clothing)	2.86	.499	Agree
2	My parents find it difficult to meet our needs at home	2.64	.553	Agree
3	My parents can't afford to buy my textbook	2.67	.618	Agree
4	My parents are too poor to cater for my school fees	2.73	.477	Agree
5	I hawk after school hours to support my school needs	2.50	.526	Agree
6	I am attending public school because my parents can't afford private high school fees	2.92	.508	Agree
7	My parents pay for other school monies order than school fees	2.45	.548	Disagree
8	My parents always give me pocket money for school	2.78	.500	Agree
9	I experience stress due to financial limitations	2.72	.505	Agree
10	I have access to support systems (e.g., family, community resources) when facing financial hardships	2.75	.552	Agree
Sectional Mean		2.70	0.528	Agree

As shown in Table 2, the socioeconomic background of senior secondary school students in North Central Nigeria was presented. The Table shows a sectional mean of 2.70, which indicates that over an average of the respondents agreed with all items on the socioeconomic background of senior secondary school students in North Central, Nigeria, except for item 7, which was disagreed. Therefore, parents of senior secondary school students in North-Central, Nigeria, are from a low socioeconomic background.

Research Question Three: *What is the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North Central Nigeria?*

Table 3: Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in North Central Nigeria in Mathematics and English Language from 2020-2024

Year & Geo-political Zone	Total No. of students who sat for the exam	Male	Female	5credits with Math& Eng.	(%)	5credits with Math	(%)	5 credits with Eng.	(%)	5 credits without Math & Eng.	(%)
2020/2021 North-Central	256,426	136,103	120,323	225,791	88.1	116,927	45.6	108,864	42.4	30,635	11.9
2021/2022 North-Central	274,864	144,808	130,056	210,531	76.6	104,871	38.1	105,660	38.4	64,333	23.4
2022/2023 North-Central	248,207	127,918	120,289	174,498	70.7	631,09	24.7	111,389	25.4	73,709	29.7
2023/2024 North-Central	294,104	154,823	139,281	215,168	73.1	833,82	28.4	131,786	28.4	78,936	26.8

As shown in Table 3, the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North Central Nigeria, in Mathematics and English Language from 2020 to 2024 West African Examination Council (WAEC), was examined. The Table shows that in 2020/2021, out of the total number of students who sat

for WAEC, 88.1% obtained 5 credits and above, including English and Mathematics, 45.6% obtained 5 credits and above, including Mathematics, 42.4% obtained 5 credits and above, including English language, while 11.9% obtained 5 credits and above without English and Mathematics. In 2021/2022, the Table revealed that 76.6% obtained 5 credits and above, including English and Mathematics, 31.8% obtained 5 credits and above, including Mathematics, 38.4% obtained 5 credits and above, including English language, while 23.4% obtained 5 credits and above without English and Mathematics.

In 2022/2023, the Table equally revealed that 70.7% obtained 5 credits and above, including English and Mathematics, while 24.7% obtained 5 credits and above, including Mathematics, 25.4% obtained 5 credits and above, including English language, while 29.7% obtained 5 credits and above without English and Mathematics. Similarly, in 2023/2024, the Table also revealed that 73.1% obtained 5 credits and above, including English and Mathematics, 28.4% obtained 5 credits and above, including Mathematics, 28.4% obtained 5 credits and above, including English language, while 26.8% obtained 5 credits and above without English and Mathematics.

Therefore, based on the WAEC results from 2020 - 2024, the academic achievement of students in North-Central, Nigeria, showed some level of fluctuation within four years, although the performance remained relatively strong.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North Central Nigeria.

Table 4 Correlation Analysis between Parental Involvement and Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in North-central Nigeria

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	r-cal	p-value	Decision
Parental Involvement and Academic Achievement	384	2.67	.16	.116	.039	Rejected

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed) PPMCC

As shown in Table 4, a correlation analysis between parental involvement and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central Nigeria was presented. The Table revealed a mean of 2.67 with a standard deviation of .16 and an r value of .116. The Table also indicated a p-value of .039 with $p < 0.05$. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected. This signifies that there is a significant relationship between parental involvement and the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between the socioeconomic background on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North Central Nigeria.

Table 5: Correlation Analysis between Socioeconomic Background and Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in North-central Nigeria

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	r-cal	p-value	Decision
Socioeconomic Background and Academic Achievement	384	2.70	.17	.121	.017	Rejected

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed), PPMCC

As shown in Table 5, a correlation analysis between socioeconomic background and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central Nigeria was presented. The Table revealed a mean of 2.70 with a standard deviation of .19 and an r value of .121. The Table further indicated a p-value of .017 with $p < 0.05$. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between socioeconomic background and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship among parental involvement, socioeconomic background and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North Central Nigeria

Table 6a: Model Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis among Parental Involvement, Socioeconomic Background and Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students

Model	R	R ² Square	Adjusted R ² Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.145 ^a	.021	.013	10.15203

As shown in Table 6a, the model summary of multiple regression analysis among parental involvement, socioeconomic background and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central Nigeria was presented. The Table revealed an R value of .145^a, which is a measure of the quality of the prediction of the dependent variable, with an R² - value of .021, which indicates a moderate influence of parental involvement, and socioeconomic background on students' academic achievement. The adjusted R² Square shows the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variables. The Table further shows an adjusted R² square value of .013 which indicates that 13% of the variability of the dependent variable (academic achievement) can be explained on the basis of the independent variables (parental involvement and socioeconomic background).

Table 6b: ANOVA Analysis of Dominant Influence of Parental Involvement and Socioeconomic Background on Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
1 Regression	842.772	3	280.924	2.726	.044	Rejected
Residual	39164.186	380	103.064			
Total	40006.958	383				

Dependent Variable: Academic Achievement

Predictors: (Constant), Parental Involvement and Socioeconomic Background.

As shown in Table 6b, an ANOVA analysis to determine the dominant influence between parental involvement and socioeconomic background on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central Nigeria was presented. The Table indicated a mean square of 280.924 and 103.064 with an F-value of 2.726. The Table further revealed a significant value of 0.044, with $p < 0.05$, indicating that the hypothesis was rejected. This indicates that socioeconomic background had a more dominant influence on academic achievement than parental involvement.

Table 6c: Coefficients Analysis of Parental Involvement and Socioeconomic Background on Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1 (Constant)	2.087	13.478			.155	.877
Parental Involvement	5.302	3.132			1.974	.035
Socioeconomic Background	6.576	2.697	.108		2.439	.015
			.124			

a. Dependent Variable: Academic Achievement

As shown in Table 6c, the coefficients analysis of family structure, parental involvement, and socioeconomic background on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North Central Nigeria was presented. The Table revealed a parental involvement standardised coefficient of .108 with a significant value of .035. The Table further indicated a socioeconomic background

standardised coefficient of .124 with a significant value of .015. This implies that there is a significant relationship among parental involvement, socioeconomic background and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central Nigeria.

DISCUSSIONS

The findings of the study reveal high parental involvement of senior secondary school students in North-central Nigeria. This is consistent with Umeana (2017), who asserted that some parents actively engage in their children's education by providing emotional support, guidance, providing necessary school supplies, assisting with homework, modelling desired behaviour, engaging in reading activities with their children and maintaining an open dialogue about school events and experiences. Umeana further identified eight variables that characterize parent's active involvement in their children's education: providing emotional support, guidance, and resources, providing necessary school supplies, assisting with homework, modelling desired behaviour, engaging in reading activities with their children and maintaining an open dialogue about school events and experiences. Oranga et al. (2023) also highlighted that parental involvement in education is a critical family variable that influences the academic development of students. In a similar vein, Gidado and Diffang (2023) opined that the family is an essential, responsive and fundamental unit of society with the cardinal responsibility of improving every member of the unit positively for the betterment of society, including those within the immediate environment of the family. However, Emaimo et al. (2019) revealed that parents were not involved in their children's education due to high job commitment, lack of knowledge, and among others.

The findings of the study also indicate that parents of senior secondary school students in North-Central, Nigeria, are from a low socioeconomic background. The finding is in agreement with Kamalpreet (2018), who found that secondary school students perceive their parents differently on dimensions of parent-student relationship with reference to their income, level of education, and occupation, reflecting their access to resources, opportunities and academic success. Pal et al. (2016) also highlighted that parents' socioeconomic background is a vital determinant of the academic success of students. They further posited that parents need available resources to provide their children with a variety of services and goods that can positively improve their all-around development. Munir et al. (2023) emphasised that socio-economic status is the social and financial status of individuals or family members within a particular society. Socio-economic status can be measured using indicators such as income level of parents, parental education, and occupational status, which reflect an individual's access to resources and social prestige (Pal et al., 2016).

The findings equally reveal that the academic achievement of students in North-Central, Nigeria, showed some level of fluctuation within four years, although the performance remained relatively strong. This finding is in agreement with Razzaq et al. (2024), who indicated relatively strong academic achievements of students at the higher secondary school level. Similarly, Munir et al. (2023) also revealed a fluctuating academic achievement of secondary school students with a relatively strong performance. However, the findings of this study are in variance with Adebayo and Ojo (2025), who indicated low performance of the students in the Nigerian Senior School Certificate Examination Multiple-choice Objective Tests in Government for the years 2021 – 2023. Tshering and Chencho (2022) emphasised that this decline in performance could be attributed to poor foundation and lack of interest, repetition of classes and lack of adequate knowledge in particular subjects, especially English Language, Mathematics, the Sciences and/or Vocational and Technical subjects.

The findings also indicate a significant relationship between parental involvement and the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central Nigeria. This is in line with Sandeep and Choudhuri (2017), who reported that parental high educational expectations for children have the strongest impact on academic performance compared with other types of parental involvement constructs such as participation in school events, parent-child communication and help in homework. Similarly, Kantova (2024) indicates that higher parental involvement is associated with an increased probability of high school graduation, while stricter parental behaviour is found to decrease the expected likelihood of

completing high school. Pal et al. (2016) also opined that parents' socioeconomic background is a vital determinant of the academic success of students.

The findings equally reveal a significant relationship between socioeconomic background and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North Central Nigeria. The finding is in agreement with Munir et al. (2023), who showed that socio-economic position impacts the academic performance of students since the higher socio-economic students fare better academically than the lower socio-economic students. Similarly, Aina (2023) reported that disparity in income, education levels and occupational status among families in Nigeria creates unequal access to educational resources. These economic inequalities are aggravated by regional disparities and the growing population of out-of-school children (Ololade et al., 2023). However, the findings of this study contradict Machebe et al. (2017), who reported that the educational development of students in Japan was relatively the same irrespective of their parents' high, medium or low level of income. Their report further revealed that there is no positive relation between family income and students' academic achievement, and that the low socioeconomic background of parents did not limit the number of children who got enrolled in school.

The findings also show a significant relationship among parental involvement, socioeconomic background and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central Nigeria. This is in accordance with Njoku (2020), who revealed that parental low income, lack of high qualification, low occupational status and poor parental involvement have mutable effects on their children's academic accomplishments irrespective of their geographical location. Similarly, Gobena (2018) revealed that parental involvement level contributed 40.96% to students' academic achievement, and 59.04% unexplained variables contributed to students' academic achievement as well. Munir et al. (2023) equally stated that socio-economic status and class impact the academic performance of students since higher socio-economic status students fare better academically than the low socioeconomic students.

CONCLUSION

Arising from the findings of this study, the following conclusions are drawn: The higher parental involvement among students, the higher the academic achievement and vice versa. Most parents in the study area are from a low socioeconomic background, which in turn has a correlation with academic achievement. The relationship among parental involvement, socioeconomic background and academic achievement of students in public schools in North Central Nigeria showed a significant correlation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Parents and guardians should sustain their level of involvement in their children's education by periodically communicating with the school on appropriate strategies for addressing any challenges that their children may face in school.
2. School administrators and other stakeholders should provide aids and support such as scholarships, grants, financial assistance, free tutoring, or mentorship programmes to students from low socioeconomic backgrounds.
3. Administrators and teachers should establish a system that monitors the progress of students' performance while also considering the impact of home and school-related factors that are equally part of the root causes in the fluctuation in academic achievement of students.
4. School administrators should encourage and devise means for parents to attend school-related programmes such as parents-teachers conferences, seminars and workshops.
5. School administrators should provide support programmes such as school fees wavers or other forms of assistance to students from low socioeconomic backgrounds, which could contribute to enhancing their academic achievement.
6. School administrators and teachers should take into consideration the significant connection between parental involvement and socioeconomic background when developing interventions that enhance students' academic achievement.

REFERENCES

- Adebayo, A. & Ojo B. (2025). Analysis of Students' Academic Performance in 2021-2023 Nigerian Senior School Certificate Examination Multiple-Choice Objective Tests in Government. *International Journal of Education, Learning and Development*, 13 (5), 1-10
<https://doi.org/10.37745/ijeld.2013/vol13n5110>.
- Aina, J. (2023). Inequality of educational opportunities in Nigeria: Impacts on the national development. *Asian Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Studies*, 5(2), 28–34.
<https://doi.org/10.56557/ajahss/2022/v5i245>
- Apeh, H.A., Gidado, B. K. & Diffang, A.D. (2023). School-related factors and mental health issues amongst adolescents in public senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. *Journal of Social Studies & Civic Educators Association of Nigeria*. Vol. 5 No.1, pg. 227-234.
- Bhandari, P. (2023). *Correlational research: When and how to use*. Scribbr.
<https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/research/>
- Brew, E. A., Nketiah, B., & Koranteng, R. (2021). A literature review of academic performance: An insight into factors and their influences on academic outcomes of students at senior high schools. *Open Access Library Journal*, 8, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.4236/oalib.1107423>
- Brodowicz, M. (2024). *The importance of education in modern society*. <https://aithor.com/essay-examples/the-importance-of-education-in-modern-society-3>
- Emaimo, J., Okorie, P., & Ottun, K. (2019). Factors influencing the poor academic performances of primary school pupils living in foster homes in Aba, Abia State, Nigeria. *IDAN Journal of Development Administration*, 4(1), 1–16. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/34902899>
- Eriksson K, Lindvall J, Helenius O & Ryve A (2021) Socioeconomic Status as a Multidimensional Predictor of Student Achievement in 77 Societies. *Front. Educ.* 6:731634.
 doi: 10.3389/educ.2021.731634
- Gidado, B. K., & Diffang, A. D. (2023). Family Dysfunction and Parental Role Abdication as redispensing Factors for Drug Abuse among Secondary School Adolescents and Youths in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Science & Humanities Research*. Vol. 6, issue 6 pp. 1-12. 10.5281/zenodo.7998101.
- Gidado, B.K., & Diffang, A. D. (2024). Relationship Among Home Background Factors, Conduct Disorder and Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Evaluation*, vol. 10 No 1 pp. 487-497.
 DOI: 10.56201/ijee.v10
- Gidado, B. K., & Anyio, B. T. (2025). Influence of parenting styles on conduct disorder among secondary school students in north-central Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Research in Developing Areas*, 6(2), 55 - 67. <https://doi.org/10.47434/JEREDA.6.2.2025.55>.
- Gobena, G. A. (2018). Family socio-economic status effect on students' academic achievement at College of Education and Behavioral Sciences, Haramaya University, Eastern Ethiopia. *Journal of Teacher Education and Educators*, 7(3), 207–222.
- Kamalpreet, K. T. (2018). Parent-Child Relationship and Students' Academic Achievement: A Study of Secondary School Students. *MIER Journal of Educational Studies Trends and Practices*, 8(1), 38–56. <https://doi.org/10.52634/mier/2018/v8/i1/1418>
- Kantova, K. (2024). Parental involvement and education outcomes of their children. *Applied Economics*, 56(48), 5683–5698. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00036846.2024.2314569>
- Kim, J., Prempeh, A., Addai, E., & Wargo, E. (2023). Empowering futures: The interplay of education, employment, and income. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and management*, 37, 4–20.
- Machebe, H., C., Ezegbe, B. & Onuoha, J. C. (2017). The Impact of Parental Level of Income on Students' Academic Performance in High School in Japan. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*. 5. 1614-1620. 10.13189/ujer.2017.050919.

- Meadan, H., Angel, M. E., Stoner, J. B., & Daczewitz, M. (2014). Parent-implemented social-pragmatic communication intervention: A pilot study. *Focus on Autism and Other Developmental Disabilities*, 29(2), 95–110. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1088357613517504>
- Munir, J., Faiza, M., Jamal, B., Daud, S., & Iqbal, K. (2023). The impact of socioeconomic status on academic achievement. *Journal of Social Sciences Review*, 3(2), 695–705. <https://doi.org/10.5s4183/jssr.v3i2.308>.
- Nato, P. (2016). Analysis of Family Structure Influence on Academic Performance Among Secondary School Students in Bungoma East Sub-County, Kenya. *International Journal of Secondary Education*. 4. 12. 10.11648/j.ijssedu.20160402.11.
- Njoku, U. E. (2020), Influence of family structures and parental education on the Psychosocial adjustments of adolescents Inebonyi state secondary School. *Unizik Journal of Educational Research and Policy Studies*. <http://sjifactor.com/passport.php?id=21363>
- Oba-Adenuga, O. A. (2020). Effect of family structure on academic performance of secondary school students in Somolu Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria. *Benin Journal of Educational Studies*, 26(1 & 2).
- Ololade, E. A., Hamad, N., Adeleke, I., Udochukwu, C. N., & Nwokocha, G. (2023). Socio-economic disparities in early childhood education: A review of evidence from Nigeria and the UK. *Social Values and Society*, 107, 102744. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssresearch.2022.102744>
- Oranga, J., Matere, A., & Nyakundi, E. (2023). Importance and types of parental involvement in education. *Open Access Library Journal*, 10, e10512. <https://doi.org/10.4236/oalib.1110512>
- Qhaireenizzati. (2017). Sample size determination using Krejcie and Morgan Table. <https://qhaireenizzati.wordpress.com/2017/10/05/sample-size-determination-using-krejcie-and-morgan-table/>
- Pal, A., Manna, S. & Dhara, P. (2016). Effect of Socio-Economic Status on Learning Ability of Bengali (Indian) Primary School Children. *Advances in Applied Physiology*, 1(1), 12-17. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.aap.20160101.13>
- Razzaq, H. A. R., Majeed, M. F. M., & Bajwa, M. S. A. B. (2024). Relationship between socioeconomic status and academic achievements. *UCP Journal of Humanities & Social Sciences*, 2(2), 73–88. <https://ojs.ucp.edu.pk/index.php/jhss/article/view/190>
- Reich, J., Hein, S., Krivulskaya, S., Hart, L., Gumkowski, N., & Grigorenko, E. L. (2013). Associations between household responsibilities and academic competencies in the context of education accessibility in Zambia. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 27, 10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2013.02.005>
- Sandeep, K. J., & Choudhuri, R. (2017) A review of the relationship between parental involvement and students' academic performance. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology* 4 (3), 110-123,
- Tshering, G. & Chenchu, D. (2022). Academic Performance of Day Scholars Versus Boarders in Norbugang Central School". *Acta Scientific Pediatrics* 5.5 (2022): 15-23. 77y
- Umeana, F. P. (2017). Parental engagement with schools and students in Nigeria. <https://doi.org/doi:10.25335/1kmn-eb40>
- Utami, A. Y. (2022). The role of parental involvement in student academic outcomes. *Journal of Education Review Provision*, 2(1), 17–21. <https://doi.org/10.55885/jerp.v2i1.156>